

Analysing the role of social innovation in addressing sustainability goals in the Scottish uplands and Ukrainian Carpathians

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Considerable changes have occurred in the Scottish uplands and Ukrainian Carpathians: social, including demographic (*e.g.* workers leaving); economic (renewable energy, tourism development); institutional (*e.g.* relating to new policy documents, tenure rights) and environmental (*e.g.* driven by climatic change). Some upland regions require strategies for risk prevention (*e.g.* alleviate floods, windfalls, soil erosion) and the preservation of biological, landscape and cultural diversity. For example, the decline of agriculture in some localities affects cultural landscapes via land abandonment. In other places, small private enterprises intensify wood production, *e.g.* for using biomass for energy. An expansion of small businesses (*e.g.* tourism, infrastructure or wind/hydro power), new social enterprises and social entrepreneurship (*e.g.* health care or renewable energy) and new activities (*e.g.* mountain biking) may support sustainable economic growth. However, some changes may entail environmental and social challenges to upland ecosystems and may at times threaten sustainable provision of ecosystem services.

Important research questions therefore include: How do local people residing in the Scottish uplands and Ukrainian Carpathians perceive the changes and how do they see their future? What are the pathways towards sustainability? What are the dominant attitudes to sustainable rural development and how can they be translated into policy designs and operationalised by using socially innovative tools, strategies and adaptive management practices?

The research employed a case study approach with the use of mixed methods. By addressing and comparing selected case studies in mountain areas in Scotland and Ukrainian Carpathians, it has developed a better understanding of: (i) human-environmental interactions pertaining to social-ecological systems (SES), which is considered to be crucial for the designing innovative responses to address contemporary challenges in uplands and to enhance the systems' resilience; (ii) the perception of pathways to change by relevant stakeholders to suggest tools and strategies to enhance the resilience of SES and advance the well-being outcomes derived from these; (iii) management options, policies or institutional arrangements -- responses (*e.g.* social innovations) -- to assist in overcoming the challenges and achieving the SES sustainability at a local scale.

The pilot findings indicate that deliberative governance systems can enhance the collective agreement - hierarchically, inter-sectorally and spatially - on (i) how to attain desirable trade-offs between non-marketed and provisioning ecosystem services in a locality, and across the territory and (ii) which strategies, policy instruments and management tools to use in order to promote a more sustainable delivery of ecosystem services. Participatory decision-making processes and collaborative networks, involving scientists and other relevant stakeholders, can assist in the development of a better understanding of the drivers and pathways of change, and of how these drivers may affect marginalised rural areas and local communities residing in these areas.

Pathways to change, with opportunities and challenges that local communities in the Scottish uplands and Ukrainian Carpathians are currently facing, have been uncovered. The results offered some useful insights into innovative responses to address these challenges, including through the development of a better understanding of social innovation and linked novel governance mechanisms, specifically in the context of rural development; advancing the knowledge of success factors and the subsequent enhancement of social innovations in rural areas in the uplands.

***Acknowledgement:** We would like to thank the Scottish Government who supported this research through their Rural Affairs and the Environment Strategic Research Programme and the European Commission for support to the project on Social Innovation in Marginalised Rural Areas (SIMRA) provided from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 677622.*